

THE EFFECT OF BANK CREDIT ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE USING CAPITAL AS A MEDIATING VARIABLE IN A SAMPLE OF IRAQI COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract:

The study aimed to identify the impact of bank credit on financial performance using capital as a mediating variable in a sample of Iraqi commercial banks. The researcher used the descriptive analytical approach, and used data analysis for five Iraqi commercial banks. The most important results of the study were as follows: The results of the study showed that the capital affected the investment in shares and not vice versa, the shareholders' equity affected the deposits in this period and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the investment in shares in this period and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the total assets in this period and not the other way around, the deposits affected On investing in shares during this period and not vice versa, the total assets affected the investment in shares during this period and not vice versa. The credit did not directly affect the financial performance variables, but rather it indirectly through the capital (the intermediate variable). We also note that the credit affected the shareholders' equity in the previous period and the current period. We also note that the mediating capital variable affected the financial performance variables in Fiscal period and prior periods.

Keywords: credit, capital, financial performance

1. Introduction

The current and future changes and developments that have occurred in the business environment of economic units have led to a change in the traditional view of the nature of the mutual relationship between the bank and the society in which it operates. And similar financial institutions due to the nature of their financial resources, which necessitate the use of appropriate policies, and the impact of these developments and changes was reflected in the performance appraisal method applied to banks, and made it the subject of many questions, as its suitability for use and the effectiveness of the information obtained from it for the purposes of control, decision-making and competition, continuity in the local and global market.

Credit is one of the most important activities and businesses offered by commercial banks to clients, as it is the main activity for which the bank was established for futures. Credit is the main source of returns and profits in banks, and it directly affects the results of the financial performance of these banks. Because of its importance, each bank sets a credit policy. It is represented in a set of decisions issued by the bank's senior management, in which it defines the criteria for granting bank credit granted by the bank.

Banks are among the most important financial institutions operating in the country, as they are the mainstay in order to achieve economic growth and development in them. Therefore, the activities of banks are distinguished from other economic activities by the diversity and multiplicity of services, and accordingly, measuring the financial performance of these banks is one of the basic and necessary operations for the continuation of the operations. The Bank's activity and to face the continuous changes and challenges.

There are many indicators that measure the financial performance of banks, including the shareholder's equity ratio, the bank's deposits, the net profit ratio, the percentage of investment on shares, the total assets, the better the bank's financial performance.

The banking sector in Iraq is one of the most important components of the Iraqi banking system, and many commercial and Islamic banks, both national and expatriate, work in it. The number of commercial banks listed on the Stock Exchange is (40) banks. These banks must abide by and abide by the instructions of the Central Bank of Iraq authority, and draw up clear banking policies for them that work on developing deposits and employing the money of shareholders and investors in the bank in well-studied investment activities.

Given the importance of the topic, the title of this study was chosen to identify the impact of credit on financial performance variables using capital as a mediating variable in a sample of banks listed in Iraqi securities, namely (Ashur International Bank for Investment, North Bank for Finance and Investment, Gulf Commercial Bank of Iraq, Al Ahli Bank Al-Iraqi and the Commercial Bank of Baghdad) based on a set of related financial indicators, namely: property rights, net profit margin, investments in stocks, deposits and total assets.

Based on the foregoing, the research problem can be summarized in the following question: What is the effect of credit on financial performance using capital as a mediating variable in a sample of Iraqi commercial banks for the period (2006-2020).

The study seeks to identify the impact of the volume of credit on the financial performance of banks, and to determine the impact of capital on the financial performance of banks.

Theoretical framework

2. Concept of bank credit.

Bank credit is considered the most important element in the bank's returns if it is compared to other elements on the one hand, and on the other hand it is of great benefit in providing the various economic sectors in society, including individuals, establishments, and institutions, with the funds necessary to carry out their activities.¹

The term bank credit refers to the amount of credit available to business or individuals from a banking institution in the form of loans, therefore, bank credit is the total amount of money that any person or company can borrow from a bank or other financial institution, the bank credit of the borrower depends on his ability to repay Any loans and the total amount of credit available for lending by the banking institution. Types of bank credit include car loans, personal loans, and mortgages.²

Banks and financial institutions make money from the money they lend to their customers. This money comes from money customers deposit in their checking and savings accounts or invest in certain investment vehicles such as certificates of deposit (CDs). In exchange for using their services, banks pay customers a small amount of interest on their deposits. As noted, this money is lent to others and is known as bank credit.³

Bank credit consists of the total amount of pooled funds provided by financial institutions to individuals or companies. It is an agreement between banks and borrowers whereby banks make loans to borrowers. By extending credit, the bank essentially trusts the borrowers to repay the principal balance as well as interest at a later date. Whether someone is approved for credit and how much money they get depends on an assessment of their creditworthiness.⁴

Approval is determined by the borrower's credit rating, income, or other considerations. This includes collateral, assets or the amount of debt they already have. There are several ways to secure approval, including lowering the total debt-to-income (DTI) ratio. An acceptable DTI is 36%, but 28% is ideal. Borrowers are generally encouraged to keep card balances at 20% or less of the credit limit and pay off all delinquent accounts. Banks typically offer credit to borrowers with a hostile credit history on terms that benefit the banks themselves—higher interest rates, fewer lines of credit, and more restrictive terms.⁵

Bank credit is defined as a loan granted for the business requirements or personal needs of its customers, with or without collateral or security, with the expectation of earning periodic interest on the loan amount. The principal amount shall be refunded at the end of the loan term, duly agreed upon, and mentioned in the loan agreement.⁶

Bank credit is granted to the borrowers for fulfilling the necessary documents required by the bank. The interest rates and repayment terms are duly mentioned in the loan agreement. Bank documentation includes: ⁷

- Financial Statements.
- Income tax returns.
- Expected financial statements for a period of three to five years.
- Changes depend on the type of loan and from person to person.

Bank credit is of two types: loan and credit. The loan means: providing a certain amount of money in one go by the bank to the customer. As for the credit, it is a pledge by the bank to put an amount of money at the customer's disposal during a certain period to withdraw from it what he wants, and he does not pay interest. Except for the amounts actually used, and each of the three words: credit, credit, loan, and is translated in French as Credit. However, the loan can be used for another synonym, which is Pret. The concept of bank credit also defines as the trust that the bank places on a person, whether natural or moral, by giving him a sum of money to use for a specific purpose during an agreed period of time and on certain conditions in return for an agreed upon material return. And with guarantees that enable the bank to recover its loan in the event the customer stops paying.”

3. Concept of financial performance:

The financial performance is the extent to which the company succeeds in making the best use of its available material and moral resources and trying to reach the pre-planned goals of the company's management.⁸

Financial performance is defined as the extent to which the activities carried out by companies contribute to creating value or effectiveness in using the available financial resources by achieving financial goals at the lowest costs.⁹

The concept of financial performance is closely related to strategic management because it evaluates the performance of the company's management using a set of short and long-term financial and non-financial indicators.¹⁰

It also defined financial performance as a measure of the extent to which assets are used to achieve and generate revenue. It is used as a general measure to know the integrity of the overall financial position of the institution during a specific period, and it can be used to compare the performance of institutions for the same sector or between different sectors or industries, and there are many different methods for measuring financial performance, where revenues from operations, operating income, operating cash flows can be used. , sales in gross units, and profit margin growth rate, but all measures should be taken holistically.¹¹

He also defined financial performance as “the extent to which the institution is able to exploit its resources and resources in long-term and short-term uses in order to form wealth through appropriate information and a practical and scientific method of analysis in building indicators.¹²

“Financial performance” represents the narrow concept of the performance of institutions, as it focuses on the use of financial indicators to measure the extent to which goals are achieved.¹³

Financial performance is defined as an integrated system that compares the actual results of the selected or elected indicators with the corresponding target indicators, or those that reflect the performance results during a previous period, or the performance results in similar economic units, taking into account the historical and structural conditions.¹⁴

Financial performance is defined as the results of the outputs that are obtained from operations and products. It expresses the outputs or goals that the system seeks to achieve. It is a concept that reflects both the goals and the means necessary to achieve them, that is, it links between the aspects of activity and the goals that the organization seeks to achieve.¹⁵

The researcher believes that financial performance is the financial procedures and activities carried out by the institution to achieve the planned financial goals, and it can be measured by many means, and the results of this measurement are important for all aspects of financial planning such as forecasting, risk management and working capital management, and performance may be good or bad based on a comparison Actual performance as planned. The researcher believes that this last definition includes several elements, namely: ¹⁶

- Its ability to define good or bad performance, not just one of them.

- Its ability to define the performance of for-profit and non-profit organizations
- Differentiating between the nature of performance, its objective and its importance.

Statistical analysis and hypothesis testing

This section includes analyzing the data and testing the hypotheses of the study, through a presentation analyzing the data obtained, reviewing the most prominent results that were reached, and identifying the study variables. Statistical analysis (EViews) to obtain the results of the study that were presented and analyzed in this topic, and the following is a detail of that.

1. The methodology used.

The study method is the method followed by the researcher to reach results related to the topic under study. The researcher relied on the descriptive analytical method in the theoretical aspect of the study, while the applied aspect related to the standard study used the quantitative approach through the use of longitudinal time series data (Data Panel). Which represents data on a group of banks during a certain period of time, using the statistical program Eviews mainly to apply all statistical and standard methods.

2. Study community.

The study population is represented in all the banks listed in the Iraqi stock market, which are (5) banks, namely: Ashur International Bank, North Bank for Investment and Finance, Khaleeji Commercial Bank, National Bank of Iraq, and Bank of Baghdad, all of which are registered banks in the Iraqi stock market and a component It is essential for the Iraqi banking system, and it has branches spread in Baghdad and the governorates, during the time period (2006-2020), noting that the financial statements of the study community are fully available during the study period.

3. Methods of data collection.

This was done through secondary sources to obtain the data necessary to formulate the theoretical side of the subject of the study and the data used in the analysis. These data were obtained through the following sources:

- Arab and foreign references from books, periodicals, articles, seminars and scientific papers that dealt with creditworthiness, sustainable growth rate and financial performance of banks.
- The annual reports and financial statements of the banks listed on the Iraqi stock market in the period 2006-2020 through the official website of each bank and the Iraqi stock market, in order to access the data necessary to measure the impact of creditworthiness on the relationship between the rate of sustainable growth and the financial performance of a sample of Iraqi banks.

4. Model description.

The first and most important steps of standard scientific research when studying an economic phenomenon is the description of the model, that is, the expression of the economic theory in a mathematical way in the form of an equation:

- Identification of variables: variables and their symbols used in the analysis can be identified; how many in table (1).

Table (1): Determine the variables

Variables	Variable names and symbols
independent variable (credit)	Cr= credit.
Mediator Variable (Capital)	Ca = capital.
Performance (financial performance)	Ta = total assets
	IS = equity investments
	De= deposit
	Co = shareholder equity.
	Pr= net profit

5. Time series inactivity test.

The Decker-Fuller test was used to verify the stability of the time series and to determine the degree of integration of each series (the degree of stability), and the following table shows that:

Table (2): Decker-Fuller test results for study variables

difference level	variable value	probability level	Variable
The second difference	-3.939	-3.144	Ca
The second difference	-3.841	-3.175	Co
The second difference	-5.009	-3.144	Cr
The first difference	-5.466	-3.144	De
The first difference	-5.198	-3.175	Is
The first difference	-3.451	-3.098	Pr
The first difference	-3.411	-3.119	Total

* Significant at 5% significance level.

Through the results of the expanded Decker-Fuller test above, it was found that the variables are stable in the first and second difference, except for the variable net profit, which stabilized at the level, at a significant level of 5%.

Eighth: hypothesis testing.

- The first model: net profit is a function of credit and capital.

$$Pr=F (Cr,Ca)$$

Table (3): First Model (Net Profit is a Function of Credit and Capital)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	0.018321	1.018321	0.016936	0.9868
Log (Ca)	0.362339	0.271365	1.335244	0.2066
Log (Cr)	0.107189	0.196703	0.544920	0.5950

Source: Program-9 Eviews

We note from the results of the above table that the independent variable credit and the median variable capital currently did not affect the dependent variable, the net profit currently from this period.

- Co-integration (Bounds Test)

The results of the Bounds Test were that the variables are integrated from the long run. This shows through the value of 3.90 with the value of Bounds at the 5% level of significance, which amounted to 3.79

Table (4): The adopted model of the co-integration equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
Pr(-1)	-1.067510	0.319037	-0.345519	0.007

The results of the estimated model for the joint integration equation Bounds Test indicated that the independent variable credit and the median variable capital currently affect the net profit, which reflects the sustainable growth for previous periods.

Error Correction Form:

Table No. (5): cointegrating form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
cointfq(-1)	-1.177	0.32001	-3.680037	0.004

Through the results of the error correction model, it became clear that the error is corrected by 117% in the short term, up to an integration in the long term.

- The second model: total assets as a function of credit and capital

$$TA=F(cr,ca)$$

Table (6): Total assets as a function of credit and capital

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	1.444811	0.0400306	3.609264	0.003
Log (Ca)	0.847047	0.100418	8.435216	0.000
Log (Cr)	-0.020046	0.072789	-0.275402	0.7877

We note from the results of the above table that the mediating variable, which is the capital, affected the total assets.

Also, from the median variable, capital, affected the total assets by 90%, it appears through the value of R2. We also note that the model concluded from the problem of autocorrelation, this appears through the value of D-W, which amounted to 1.38.

• Co-integration (Bounds Test)

The results of the Bounds Test indicated that the variables are not integrated in the long run. This is shown by the value of the value, which amounted to 1.80 to less than 3.79 for the 5% level of significance.

Error Correction Form:

Table No. (7): cointegrating form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
cointfq(-1)	-0.993460	0.265649	-3.739743	0.004

The results of the above model indicated that the error is corrected by 99% up to the integration in the long run.

• The third model: Deposits are a function of credit and capital.

$$De=F(cr,ca)$$

Table (8): Deposits are a function of credit and capital

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	0.670855	0.075593	-0.623707	0.5445
Log (Ca)	1.065922	0.269816	3.950555	0.0019
Log (Cr)	0.109532	0.195580	-0.560039	0.5858

The results of the above table indicated that the median variable, the capital, affected the deposits in this period. This is shown by the value of (0.0001) = prob.

It is statistically significant. We also note that the median variable has an effect of 63%. We also note that the problem of autocorrelation is solved and this is shown by the value of D-W, which amounted to 1.08.

• Co-integration (Bounds Test)

The results of the Bounds Test indicated that the variables are not integrated in the long run. This is shown by the value of the test, which amounted to 3.54 to less than 3.79 for a significant level of 5%

Table (9): Estimated Model of Cointegration Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
DE(-1)	-0.945710	0.29799	-3.179936	0.0098

The results of the estimated model of the joint integration equation Bounds Test indicated that the independent variable credit and the median variable capital in the current period affect the total deposits in previous periods.

Error Correction Form:

Table No. (10): cointegrating form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
TuEq(-1)	0.929197	0.272343	-3.411863	0.0066

The results of the above model indicated that the error is corrected by 92% from the short term to integration in the long term.

- The fourth model: investment in shares is a function of credit and capital.

Is=F (cr,ca)

Table (11): Investment in stocks is a function of credit and capital

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	1.895669	3.025449	0.626575	0.542
Log (Ca)	-0.070591	0.758943	-0.093013	0.927
Log (Cr)	0.139535	0.550131	0.253639	0.8041

We note from the results of the above table that credit and capital in the current period did not affect the investment and the shares.

- Joint Integration (Bounds Test).

The results of the Bounds Test indicate that the variables are integrated in the long run, as shown by the value of 7.09.

Table (12): Estimated Model of Cointegration Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
IS(-1)	-1.040761	0.236402	-4.402500	0.0017

The results of the above table indicated that credit and capital affected the investment in shares for a previous period.

Error Correction Form:

Table No. (13): cointegrating form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
Coint(-1)	-0.659086	0.170732	-3.860351	0.0036

Through the above model, it became clear that the error is corrected by 65%, up to the integration in the long run.

- The fifth model: shareholders' equity as a function of credit and capital.

$$Co=F(cr,ca)$$

Table (14): Shareholders' equity as a function of credit and capital

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	0.413700	0.119704	3.456017	0.0048
Log (Ca)	0.928814	0.030028	30.93138	0.0000
Log (Cr)	0.007547	0.021766	0.346766	0.7348

The results of the above table indicated that the capital affected the equity of the shareholders. This is shown by (0.000000) Prob that it is statistically significant. The R2 statistic also indicated that the capital affects the shareholders' equity by 99%, as indicated by the value of D-W. The model concluded from the autocorrelation problem.

- Co-integration (Bounds Test)

The results of co-integration indicated that the variables are integrated in the long run through the value of the value, which amounted to 20.36.

Table (15): Estimated Model of Cointegration Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
D (cr)	0.283357	0.087311	3.245399	0.0118
D (ca)	1.242254	0.08838	14.05567	0.0000
C	6.209789	2.965081	2.094307	0.0696
Cr (-1)	-0.389020	0.083259	-4.672478	0.0016
Ca(-1)	1.004446	0.142095	7.068650	0.0001
Co(-1)	-0.94495	0.137457	-6.874507	0.0001

The results of the above table indicated that credit and capital affected the shareholders' equity in the long term, in the current and previous periods, and the effect of these variables was 98%.

Error Correction Form:

Table No. (16): cointegrating form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
CointEq(-1)	-0.944952	0.137457	-6.874507	0.000

The results of the above table indicated that the error is corrected by 9.4% in the short term up to integration in the long term.

- The sixth model: capital as a credit function.

$$Ca=F(Cr)$$

Table (17): Capital is a function of credit

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	3.621437	0.462150	7.836058	0.000
Log (Cr)	0.441047	0.159546	2.764317	0.0161

We note from the results of the above table that credit affected the median variable capital itself by 37%, this is shown by the value of R2 and the value of Prob, which amounted to (0.016), which is statistically significant.

- Co-integration (Bounds Test)

A value of 5.475 indicates that credit and capital are complementary in the long run.

Table No. (18): Estimated Model of the Cointegration Equation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	21.06234	10.70165	1.968140	0.7
Cr (-1)	0.647419	0.215077	3.010180	0.0119
Ca (-1)	-0.140368	0.061159	-2.295131	0.04

The results of the above table indicated that the credit in the current period and previous periods had an impact on the intermediate variable capital, the current period and previous periods.

- The seventh model: capital is indicative of all variables.

Ca=F (Co,Cr,De,Is,Pr,Ta)

Table (19): The seventh model: capital is indicative of all variables

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Test Statistic	Prob
C	-3.741703	11.22445	-0.333353	07474
Co	0.830773	0.296962	2.797576	0.0233
Cr	0.005613	0.170069	0.033005	0.9745
De	-0.201668	0.292660	-0.689084	0.5103
Is	-9.6005	0.147214	-0.000652	09995
Pr	-0.851136	1.195953	-0.711680	0.4969
Ta	0.168564	0.252714	0.667014	0.5235

Through the results of the table, it became clear that shareholders' equity affected the capital. It was noted that credit did not affect the capital in this model, and it was noted that credit affected the capital in the sixth model, but in the case of multiple regression, it became clear that the effect of the variables on each other on the credit is not moral.

This can be illustrated through the causal relationships between the variables through the following table:

Table (20): Causal Relationships between Variables

Null Hypothesis	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob
Co does not Granger Cause Ca	13	0.76364	0.4971
Ca does not Granger Cause Co		0.05529	0.9466
Cr does not Granger Cause Ca	13	2.38553	0.1540
Ca does not Granger Cause Cr		2.16623	0.1771
Dr does not Granger Cause Ca	13	0.04812	0.9533
Ca does not Granger Cause De		3.83587	0.0679
Is does not Granger Cause Ca	13	1.28304	0.3286
Co does not Granger Cause Is		16.4698	0.0015
Pr does not Granger Cause Ca	13	0.17010	0.8466
Ca does not Granger Cause Pr		0.93404	0.4319
Ta does not Granger Cause Ca	13	0.14686	0.8657
Ca does not Granger Cause Ta		1.22832	0.3426
Cr does not Granger Cause Co	13	0.17857	0.8397
Co does not Granger Cause Cr		1.89030	0.2127
De does not Granger Cause Co	13	0.05532	0.9465
Co does not Granger Cause De		5.68912	0.0290
Is does not Granger Cause Co	13	1.13645	0.3678
Co does not Granger Cause Is		14.8886	0.0020
Pr does not Granger Cause Co	13	0.20026	0.8225
Co does not Granger Cause Pr		0.44460	0.6560
Ta does not Granger Cause Co	13	0.02763	0.9728
Co does not Granger Cause Ta		4.63843	0.0460
De does not Granger Cause Cr	13	0.08239	0.9217
Cr does not Granger Cause De		0.11226	0.8952
Is does not Granger Cause Cr	13	2.11766	0.1828
Cr does not Granger Cause Is		0.77088	0.4941
Pr does not Granger Cause Cr	13	0.39937	0.6834
Cr does not Granger Cause Pr		2.54551	0.1395
Ta does not Granger Cause Cr	13	0.15700	0.8573
Cr does not Granger Cause Ta		0.83802	0.0552
Is does not Granger Cause De	13	2.18440	0.1750
De does not Granger Cause Is		4.25265	0.0552
Pr does not Granger Cause De	13	0.35322	0.0704
De does not Granger Cause Pr		0.53772	0.1163
Ta does not Granger Cause De	13	3.76596	0.0704
De does not Granger Cause Ta		2.84983	0.4971
Pr does not Granger Cause Is	13	2.50051	0.1434
Is does not Granger Cause Pr		0.76379	0.4971

Ta does not Granger Cause Is	13	11.6094	0.0043
Is does not Granger Cause Ta		0.73850	0.5078
Ta does not Granger Cause Pr	13	0.64934	0.5479
Pr does not Granger Cause Ta		0.03052	0.9701

Through the results of the above causal relationships it turns out that:

The capital affected the investment in shares and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the deposits in this period and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the investment in shares in this period and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the total assets in this period and not the other way around, the deposits affected the investment in shares In this period and not vice versa, the total assets affected the investment in shares in this period and not the other way around.

The credit did not directly affect the financial performance variables, but rather it indirectly through the capital (the intermediate variable). We also note that the credit affected the shareholders' equity in the previous period and the current period. We also note that the mediating capital variable affected the financial performance variables in Fiscal period and prior periods.

Conclusion

Financial performance is of great importance as it is one of the basic pillars of any institution in general, and banks in particular, as it is the mirror that reflects the financial position of the client or the institution requesting the loan, and it also shows the ability of the client to fulfill his obligations towards the lending bank. Commercial banks, as economic institutions, also use financial performance to a large extent, as it guides them to take sound decisions, in order to reduce the credit risks that usually accompany credit granting operations, so the bank's management studies the loan request from all sides through financial balance indicators and financial ratios , depending on the financial statements submitted by the client, in addition to providing various guarantees, and studying whether this project will bring profits to the bank or not, in order for the bank to decide in the end whether to grant the loan or not.

1. search results:

Through our treatment of the issue of the impact of bank credit on the financial performance of the bank, due to its importance in studying the financial solvency of the client, we can present the most important results as follows:

- The results of the first hypothesis were the results of the Bounds Test that the variables are integrated from the long run. This is shown through the value of 3.90 with the value of Bounds at the 5% level of significance, which amounted to 3.79. The results of the estimated model of the co-integration equation Bounds Test indicate that the independent variable is credit And the median variable, the capital currently, affects the net profit, which reflects the sustainable growth for previous periods.

- Results of the second hypothesis: We note that the mediating variable, which is the capital, affected the total assets. This is shown by the value of (0.000 Prob), without the effect of credit on the total assets.
- Results of the third hypothesis: The results of the estimated model of the joint integration equation Bounds Test indicated that the independent variable credit and the median variable capital in the current period affect the total deposits in previous periods.
- The results of the fourth hypothesis: credit and capital affected the investment in shares for a previous period.
- The results of the fifth hypothesis: credit and capital affected the equity of shareholders in the long term, the current financial period and previous periods, and the impact of these variables was 98%.
- The results of the sixth hypothesis: that credit, the current period and the previous periods had an impact on the intermediate variable capital, the current period and the previous periods.
- Results of the seventh hypothesis: that the capital affected the investment in shares and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the deposits in this period and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the investment in shares during this period and not the other way around, the shareholders' equity affected the total assets in this period and not the other way around, Deposits affected the investment in stocks in this period and not vice versa, the total assets affected the investment in stocks in this period and not the other way around.
- The credit did not directly affect the financial performance variables, but rather affected it indirectly through the capital (the intermediate variable). We also note that the credit affected the shareholders' equity in the previous period and the current period. We also note that the capital mediating variable affected the performance variables. financial in the financial period and previous periods.

2. Recommendations.

- Seeking to determine the appropriate credit ratio, which achieves the best financial performance for banks.
- Ensuring the ability of credit holders to fulfill their obligations towards the bank, so that this credit does not become bad debts that negatively affect the financial performance of the banks.
- Seeking to reduce the expenses associated with the credit process, in order to increase the revenues of the banks.
- Working on multiple forms of investment, and not limiting them to granting credit.

- Conducting other studies to identify the variables that affect the financial performance, by studying the variables in the financial statements of banks that were not addressed in the current study.

Resources

- 1) Awaysheh, A., Heron, R. A., Perry, T., & Wilson, J. I. (2020). On the relation between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 41(6), 965-987.
- 2) Barauskaite, G., & Streimikiene, D. (2021). Corporate social responsibility and financial performance of companies: The puzzle of concepts, definitions and assessment methods. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 28(1), 278-287.
- 3) Bartolacci, F., Caputo, A., & Soverchia, M. (2020). Sustainability and financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises: A bibliometric and systematic literature review. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 1297-1309.
- 4) Bezemer, D., Ryan-Collins, J., Van Lerven, F., & Zhang, L. (2018). Credit where it's due: A historical, theoretical and empirical review.
- 5) Capasso, G., Gianfrate, G., & Spinelli, M. (2020). Climate change and credit risk. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 266, 121634.
- 6) Cho, S. J., Chung, C. Y., & Young, J. (2019). Study on the Relationship between CSR and Financial Performance. *Sustainability*, 11(2), 343.
- 7) Dubyna, M., Zhavoronok, A., Kudlaieva, N., & Lopashchuk, I. (2021). Transformation of household credit behavior in the conditions of digitalization of the financial services market. *Journal of Optimization in Industrial Engineering*, 14(Special Issue), 195-201.
- 8) Gilchrist, S., Wei, B., Yue, V. Z., & Zakrajšek, E. (2020). The Fed takes on corporate credit risk: An analysis of the efficacy of the SMCCF (No. w27809). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- 9) GOFWAN, H. (2022). Effect of accounting information system on financial performance of firms: A review of literature. DEPARTMENT OF ACCOUNTING (BINGHAM UNIVERSITY)-2nd Departmental Seminar Series with the Theme–History of Accounting Thoughts: A Methodological Approach. Vol. 2, No. 1.
- 10) Gunnarsson, B. R., Vanden Broucke, S., Baesens, B., Óskarsdóttir, M., & Lemahieu, W. (2021). Deep learning for credit scoring: Do or don't?. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 295(1), 292-305.
- 11) Hannoon, A., Al-Sartawi, A., Musleh, M. A., & Khalid, A. A. (2021). Relationship between financial technology and financial performance. In *The Big Data-Driven Digital Economy: Artificial and Computational Intelligence* (pp. 337-344). Springer, Cham.
- 12) He, L., Liu, R., Zhong, Z., Wang, D., & Xia, Y. (2019). Can green financial development promote renewable energy investment efficiency? A consideration of bank credit. *Renewable Energy*, 143, 974-984.
- 13) Ichsán, R., Suparmin, S., Yusuf, M., Ismal, R., & Sitompul, S. (2021). Determinant of Sharia Bank's Financial Performance during the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*, 298-309.
- 14) Kurbonov, K. (2021). Religious-legal bases of activity of Islamic credit institutions. *Архив научных исследований*, 1(1).
- 15) Kyere, M., & Ausloos, M. (2021). Corporate governance and firms financial performance in the United Kingdom. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(2), 1871-1885.